

Transcription Reseller Expert

00:02:13 Spreker 2

Yeah, OK, so my name is Christian.

00:02:16 Spreker 2

I finished my studies and Ichigo and.

00:02:21 Spreker 2

And I've not done anything in economics nor ITI actually studied physics.

00:02:25 Spreker 2

I'm I'm a physicist by trade or buy buy whatever and I moved into action, started working for HP when it was still 1 com.

00:02:36 Spreker 2

Funny and and uh, and I I always most of my career work with partners.

00:02:44 Spreker 2

Uhm, for a few reasons but but I I really enjoy working with partners.

00:02:51 Spreker 2

Uh, and uh, right now I'm uh, I was for the last three or four years I'm I'm working in Microsoft in, in, in the Western European area.

00:03:00 Spreker 2

Headquarter roll the Western European.

00:03:03 Spreker 2

Microsoft is what you would consider Western Europe, minors, France, UK and Germany.

00:03:06 Spreker 2

So minus the big three, but the rest would you think that's Western Europe?

00:03:09 Spreker 2

This is kind of my.

00:03:11 Spreker 2

Uh, it's it's.

00:03:12 Spreker 2

It's total 14 countries and I'm channel sales manager in this area.

00:03:18 Spreker 2

We have teams in all countries and and uh, yeah, and that's it.

00:03:23

Oh, that's alright.

00:03:25 Spreker 1

Then what's wrong?

00:03:25 Spreker 2

And I don't play water polo and I don't play tennis.

00:03:25 Spreker 1

With you.

00:03:28 Spreker 2

I like to to bike and ski.

00:03:30 Spreker 2

Of course, being Austrian.

00:03:31 Spreker 1

Of course nice nice yes.

00:03:33 Spreker 1

And what are some of the key activities that?

00:03:36 Spreker 1

You perform on your job.

00:03:38 Spreker 1

Just to start out a little bit general.

00:03:39 Spreker 2

You mean really me as a person or or what the team is doing?

00:03:44 Spreker 2

Because because my job is slightly different from what actually the people who are doing it in the countries.

00:03:48 Spreker 2

Because I'm more a headquarter guy.

00:03:51 Spreker 2

So I'm more like you know, driving things and I'm I'm I'm my I see my role I need to enable the guys have.

00:03:58 Spreker 2

In the countries.

00:03:59 Spreker 2

Which is slightly different from actually doing it.

00:04:01 Spreker 2

So, so you need to do you want?

00:04:03 Spreker 2

Me or what what, what the role is?

00:04:05 Spreker 1

Uh, let's say for this active.

00:04:05 Spreker 2

In the countries.

00:04:08 Spreker 1

So for this interview, what you?

00:04:09 Spreker 1

Doing so enabling yours.

00:04:10 Spreker 3

Right, OK.

00:04:11 Spreker 3

So yeah, maybe maybe very short.

00:04:15 Spreker 2

Sorry, what you.

00:04:16 Spreker 3

And also very short what?

00:04:17 Spreker 3

Your team does OK athlete.

00:04:18 Spreker 2

What you doing?

00:04:18 Spreker 3

Or your answers will cover both.

00:04:20 Spreker 2

Yes, OK, so so.

00:04:22 Spreker 2

So overall you know?

00:04:23 Spreker 2

Uhm, let me start with the team because that's that's, I think, a very classic thing.

00:04:27 Spreker 2

What you're doing?

00:04:28 Spreker 2

Uh, in partner sales, you know what you doing.

00:04:31 Spreker 2

Partner sales and this has fun enough, not changed or the I don't know.

00:04:35 Spreker 2

30 years I'm doing this job, although the tools and the the detail and the date and everything.

00:04:40 Spreker 2

Change, but the real job is still the same.

00:04:42 Spreker 2

What you do is you have a list of accounts you want to sell into.

00:04:45 Spreker 2

Based on whatever you know, your company.

00:04:48 Spreker 2

Like this case, Microsoft is doing segmentation in and saying OK, you're responsible for a given product to sell into given set of customers.

00:04:55 Spreker 2

Then you take these kind of you know ingredients and you go to one of the top partners.

00:05:00 Spreker 2

Someone is telling me there's the top partner in this field.

00:05:02 Spreker 2

You go to them, talk to their sales manager and say, OK, this is the list of customers.

00:05:06 Spreker 2

That's the product I want to sell in which of them do?

00:05:08 Spreker 2

You want to work with me.

00:05:10 Spreker 2

That's, uh, and and then the partner says, yeah, we are engaging these customers already.

00:05:14 Spreker 2

These customers.

00:05:15 Spreker 2

We don't know yet.

00:05:16 Spreker 2

And then you kind of work on a on a kind of a joint.

00:05:20 Spreker 2

List of target accounts.

00:05:23 Spreker 2

And then you start pursuing that by helping the partner to drive.

00:05:28 Spreker 2

I don't know marketing and sales activities into these customers, and if the partner then has a challenge or challenge, they just say, OK, this customer is interested.

00:05:35 Spreker 2

They now want to do a kind.

00:05:36 Spreker 2

For a proof of concept.

00:05:38 Spreker 2

Which is kind of a demo with.

00:05:39 Spreker 2

Them, depending on the part of their needs, then your job is a partner sellers to come back to these guys say yeah.

00:05:44 Spreker 2

Well here you get some I don't know.

00:05:46 Spreker 2

I will give you free credits for instance for Asia to drive this or you let's do a joint sales call with the customer.

00:05:54 Spreker 2

I can bring a technician in from our side too.

00:05:56 Spreker 2

Explain what the technology behind that is on our side so whatever is required to kind of advance the opportunity that has been generated and then close it by potentially.

00:06:05 Spreker 2

Also, you know I.

00:06:06 Spreker 2

Don't know certain models we can provide extra these come to a customer but whatever is required to have to partner close the deal.

00:06:12 Spreker 2

So to jointly manage the pipeline with the partner, this is classic partner sales, so this has not really changed since I started doing this again, the methods have changed and and and the data we have, we're bringing to the table.

00:06:25 Spreker 2

There's a lot of I would say targeting data which was not existing.

00:06:29 Spreker 2

You know 10 or 15 years ago, but.

00:06:30 Spreker 1

Nothing much.

00:06:32 Spreker 2

But the story is still the same.

00:06:34 Spreker 2

You know you work with sellers in the partner, uh and and then you try to close deals together.

00:06:40 Spreker 2

That's about it.

00:06:41 Spreker 1

Alright, alright Chris here so yeah.

00:06:42 Spreker 1

Just continue with them in the.

00:06:44 Spreker 1

In through the entire.

00:06:45 Spreker 1

Pipeline in order to reach customers so.

00:06:46 Spreker 2

Yes, yes.

00:06:48 Spreker 2

And so that's what, what, what, what, but very generally speaking, the team is doing on top what we're also doing is.

00:06:55 Spreker 2

Uhm, uhm.

00:06:56 Spreker 2

We're also building up capacity.

00:07:00 Spreker 2

Or are we trying to win new customer partners?

00:07:03 Spreker 2

To be honest, that's very depending on the on the product or the solution or the the service, which also why?

00:07:11 Spreker 2

Because for our model we call it modern work, which is, like, you know, office.

00:07:15 Spreker 2

365 Microsoft 365.

00:07:17 Spreker 2

So like teams, what we're using right now.

00:07:19 Spreker 2

We have a super.

00:07:20 Spreker 2

High penetration here we have literally 10 thousands of partners across the area.

00:07:25 Spreker 2

And for that we are no longer that much looking into new or additional partners, we think we're good.

00:07:31 Spreker 2

What we're trying to do here is more to kind of, you know, move partners from the very basic stuff to more high.

00:07:36 Spreker 2

End like securities.

00:07:36 Spreker 1

Well I'm selling.

00:07:38 Spreker 2

Yes, except it's about.

00:07:39 Spreker 2

Upselling and cross.

00:07:39 Spreker 2

Selling and kind of, you know, talking to partners saying, hey, you're good in this one why don't you add?

00:07:45 Spreker 2

This to your portfolio.

00:07:47 Spreker 2

This is for instance in this case when we look into our Azure or dynamics dynamics is our ERP and and CRM and whatever you call it portfolio there we have far fewer partners and This is why we're still looking for new partners where we are.

00:08:02 Spreker 2

Kind of, you know, approaching partners and saying hey, why don't?

00:08:05 Spreker 2

You work with us.

00:08:07 Spreker 2

So we can kind of jointly sell with you going forward to your customers, so that's that.

00:08:11 Spreker 2

That's the story.

00:08:11 Spreker 2

And and and Azure somewhere in the middle between these two call it extremes but but we are in Asia with both about you know, driving, upsell and cross sell.

00:08:20 Spreker 2

But also it's about driving or winning new partners still.

00:08:24 Spreker 2

So, so that's about it.

00:08:25 Spreker 2

So this is what we're also doing OK.

00:08:27 Spreker 1

Great, so this is this.

00:08:29 Spreker 1

Yeah clearly the division between already established products which you want to upsell and to invest in new partners.

00:08:35 Spreker 1

Yeah, for a lot more.

00:08:38 Spreker 1

OK.

00:08:38 Spreker 1

It is newer product.

00:08:41 Spreker 1

Right?

00:08:46 Spreker 1

But then I've got a more concrete question.

00:08:49 Spreker 1

What types of partners do exist in your ecosystem?

00:08:53 Spreker 2

Overlooked a lot, yes, so so.

00:08:56 Spreker 1

Would you give us a short list or?

00:08:58 Spreker 2

So so yes, so so.

00:09:00 Spreker 2

So first you know.

00:09:01 Spreker 2

Let let me just start with with, you know, a few which are kind of, you know, easy to understand.

00:09:05 Spreker 2

So first of all, we're working with a lot of Isvs.

00:09:08 Spreker 2

Whether these guys these are guys building the solution a packaged offer I redefine as these these are guys selling packaged solutions on top.

00:09:15 Spreker 2

Part of our, uh cloud services.

00:09:18 Spreker 2

OK, so for instance someone building a solution for I don't know for a retail solution, I'll I'll bring up here Adobe because it's one of the biggest we have world.

00:09:28 Spreker 2

But either way it's a great solution for retailers.

00:09:31 Spreker 2

Big retailers.

00:09:32 Spreker 2

Uh, uhm, this is running on top of Asia, so if if Adobe sells more we make more Azure revenue in the back end OK?

00:09:40 Spreker 2

It's super easy and another way is a global one.

00:09:42 Spreker 2

The same is true.

00:09:42 Spreker 2

For guys like.

00:09:43 Spreker 2

Barracuda with guys in every country in Europe doing the same, you know going down to very small customers and very small Isvs.

00:09:49 Spreker 2

So that's one part of the ecosystem.

00:09:51 Spreker 2

Then we have another piece which is very specific.

00:09:54 Spreker 2

This is important to engage with in our large enterprise customers.

00:09:58 Spreker 2

These are the global system integrators.

00:10:00 Spreker 2

Like century Capgemini.

00:10:01 Spreker 2

I you name it like these.

00:10:03 Spreker 2

Also, global guys typically vendor agnostic or much more than diagnostic.

00:10:09 Spreker 2

So it's it's these are, I would say partners that are, you know, and I would say challenging in the sense you know by design these guys on in diagnostics.

00:10:19 Spreker 2

So it's.

00:10:22 Spreker 1

More words that can go.

00:10:22 Spreker 2

From yeah from a vendor side.

00:10:25 Spreker 2

They are not as loyal.

00:10:26 Spreker 2

I would say which is fine because this is what the what these enterprise customers are looking for.

00:10:31 Spreker 2

Like shell.

00:10:32 Spreker 2

You know they are.

00:10:33 Spreker 2

They are, they want someone who is advising them with.

00:10:35 Spreker 2

A more neutral view.

00:10:36 Spreker 2

Because otherwise they can't go to Microsoft anyhow.

00:10:38 Spreker 2

They make account in Microsoft oh, OK, so so these are.

00:10:42 Spreker 2

These are next set global system integrators.

00:10:44 Spreker 2

Then continuing with of course you know a lot of local and small and medium sized system integrators in countries.

00:10:51 Spreker 2

There are a few that are spending a few countries in Europe like RT and the Nordics, but most of these guys are.

00:10:57 Spreker 2

I would say local guys in working in local countries OK.

00:11:01 Spreker 2

Uhm, and these are partners.

00:11:03 Spreker 2

You know between, I would say.

00:11:04 Spreker 2

I don't know 50.

00:11:06 Spreker 2

102 hundred 600 employees

00:11:09 Spreker 2

Depending on the size, but something like that, that would be a classic system.

00:11:12 Spreker 2

Integrate OK and and then we have another channel which is the telco channel.

00:11:19 Spreker 2

So this is like the operators.

00:11:20 Spreker 2

Like KPN or you name it, you know Vodafone, Telefonica and Spain.

00:11:26 Spreker 2

You know all these.

00:11:27 Spreker 2

Guys, this is also very important channel for us for this really small business customers.

00:11:32 Spreker 2

Because they can attach or you know what they're looking for is actually a way too upset to you.

00:11:38 Spreker 2

Know the margin they're making on the basic like Internet access and phone services is not high and what they want to do is they want to add products or services to.

00:11:47 Spreker 2

They are offering in order to improve the margins.

00:11:49 Spreker 2

That's it for them and and for for us as a vendor it it's a good channel because they are deeply entrenched in the very small business customers like two seats, three seats, five seats.

00:12:01 Spreker 2

Which is a very expensive channel to serve.

00:12:03 Spreker 2

Actually, if you don't have a one to many means to serve a very automated, structured way, and This is why these guys are interesting for us, so we.

00:12:11 Spreker 2

So that's also very interesting channel for us.

00:12:14 Spreker 2

Then we have another channel which and and there is obviously an overlap.

00:12:17 Spreker 2

You know it I'm I'm just explaining that you know as as if this would be super black and white, but.

00:12:22 Spreker 2

There's another channel.

00:12:23 Spreker 2

But quite some of these guys have multiple roles in the in in.

00:12:26 Spreker 2

In in the ecosystem.

00:12:28 Spreker 2

Uh, then with another channel who is selling?

00:12:30 Spreker 2

Uhm, uhm, not selling.

00:12:33 Spreker 2

They're running their own data center.

00:12:34 Spreker 2

They we we call them holster or managed service providers and these guys are running their own data centers and in their data center they're using Microsoft software.

00:12:44 Spreker 2

So for instance, they're using exchange to provide email services to their customers, but they're also using Windows Server SQL Server to provide.

00:12:51 Spreker 2

Whatever, I don't know.

00:12:53 Spreker 2

Maybe ISV solutions to their customers so Isvs around the sofa in the data center poster the host is using Microsoft as a as a as a platform, very similar to what we're doing with Asia ourselves.

00:13:04 Spreker 2

This is what hosters are doing as well, OK?

00:13:07 Spreker 2

This is especially in Western Europe.

00:13:08 Spreker 2

A very important channel.

00:13:10 Spreker 2

Uhm, uhm, compared to other areas worldwide.

00:13:14 Spreker 1

So what did you say the the first partner rose after system integrator this called?

00:13:15 Spreker 2

Yeah true.

00:13:19 Spreker 2

Particles or operators?

00:13:21 Spreker 1

Operators, thank you.

00:13:22 Spreker 2

Get stateless operators.

00:13:23 Spreker 2

Then we have hosters and then we have a very broad ecosystem, a kind of a 2 tier ecosystem are built with distributors and the results of the distributors.

00:13:34 Spreker 2

This is depending on the product.

00:13:36 Spreker 2

Extremely important for us.

00:13:38 Spreker 2

And and and there you know you you you could summarize, you know a lot of these guys.

00:13:42 Spreker 2

You know where they just said like smaller three small system integrator, small.

00:13:46 Spreker 2

Uhm, Hosters source through these distributors.

00:13:50 Spreker 2

And yeah, we also call them sometimes indirect provider because they're not directly selling to customers, but indirectly through indirect channel.

00:14:00 Spreker 2

But in the end, it's it's a classic 2 tiered distribution model that we're.

00:14:03 Spreker 2

Having here and then let me think what else?

00:14:06 Spreker 2

We have on the broader scheme we also have of course guys who are selling hardware.

00:14:10 Spreker 2

Still, because we have hardware with surface, but also keyboards and mice, and I don't know what.

00:14:19 Spreker 2

And and I think that was the last one, and then we have, you know, still classic license resellers which are more or less, you know, at least in our view, they're getting money for selling licenses to customers.

00:14:30 Spreker 2

But again, a lot of these guys move now to become system integrators or or or service provide us managing services on behalf of the customer.

00:14:39 Spreker 2

But but but the way how we define it, this would be actually a separate kind of, you know, role a partner might play OK.

00:14:47 Spreker 1

Awesome, because we also have our own list of partner roles which I will be showing right now and I think most of them overlap.

00:14:55 Spreker 1

But we also have, uh.

00:14:58 Spreker 1

Let's see, why do you?

00:14:59 Spreker 2

And I'm sorry I forgot and this is not because I'm not working with words of OEM's. Of course you know guys like HP, Lenovo, Dell.

00:15:07 Spreker 2

They're also partners of ours.

00:15:09 Spreker 2

The only thing I'm not working with them This is why I'm not not mentioning them, but but in the broader scheme of things, they obviously there as well, OK?

00:15:17

Hey good.

00:15:18 Spreker 1

Uh, yes.

00:15:19 Spreker 1

I just mentioned this is our lessons which we came up with together with, for example Joemar and Casper and literature.

00:15:29 Spreker 1

First off, we also had two independent software vendor which also what you mentioned.

00:15:34 Spreker 1

Then we also the platform provider which is more like on the architecture side instead of the software offending sites, but also a Keystone player.

00:15:44 Spreker 1

How how do you think about the platform provider?

00:15:46 Spreker 1

Do you think it's relevant, or do you think that's it's not that relevant?

00:15:52 Spreker 2

So so so.

00:15:53 Spreker 2

So I I think a lot of these guys are.

00:15:55 Spreker 2

Somewhere you know.

00:15:57 Spreker 2

That you know.

00:16:01 Spreker 2

I would say they are embedded somewhere more in this kind of global system integrators or in the system integrators.

00:16:06 Spreker 2

Because it's difficult to sell something like that.

00:16:09 Spreker 2

Unless you really like you, know you know, particularly this is the classic consultancy business I would say.

00:16:14 Spreker 2

But this is like, you know, Pricewaterhouse Coopers and catch him, you know.

00:16:17 Spreker 2

And Alan are and you link them, OK?

00:16:22 Spreker 2

Yeah, we build.

00:16:25 Spreker 1

But these could could be integrated together with the system integrator more or less because they often.

00:16:29 Spreker 2

Yes, and and then at the same time there are other guys like it depends what platform you're talking about because there are also guys that do build cloud platforms like that.

00:16:41 Spreker 2

You know, I don't.

00:16:42 Spreker 2

Know if you heard of guys called like.

00:16:43 Spreker 2

Cloud blue for instance.

00:16:45 Spreker 2

What are these guys?

00:16:45 Spreker 2

They're building cloud portals that.

00:16:49 Spreker 2

Anyone else in this ecosystem where it still codes, or whether it's a managed service providers can use to?

00:16:57 Spreker 2

Kind of, you know, sell their software to.

00:16:59 Spreker 2

Who or their services to customers and and and what these guys are doing is they are helping provision services.

00:17:07 Spreker 2

For instance, if I'm a customer of.

00:17:08 Spreker 2

A of a.

00:17:09 Spreker 2

Big hoster and I'll make it up, I don't know.

00:17:11 Spreker 2

I think STRATA 1 + 1 I don't.

00:17:12 Spreker 2

Know if you know these.

00:17:13 Spreker 2

Guys, they're very big in Europe.

00:17:14 Spreker 2

Go daily would be another example.

00:17:16 Spreker 2

For instance, OK in the US these are guys I can go to.

00:17:19 Spreker 2

The website I say I need a virtual machine or I need 5 email addresses or whatever, or I need a web server and I can just get down provision a.

00:17:26 Spreker 2

Web server and.

00:17:26 Spreker 1

Yeah, a little bit like doker offington.

00:17:30 Spreker 1

Versatel or.

00:17:31 Spreker 2

I don't know what was the name.

00:17:33 Spreker 1

Docker is for the containerization.

00:17:35 Spreker 2

No, the Docker is different.

00:17:36 Spreker 2

The Docker provides software.

00:17:37 Spreker 3

Open this.

00:17:39 Spreker 2

You know Doc is different what they are doing is they have this kind of platform where where.

00:17:44 Spreker 2

I, as a as a let me put it like that.

00:17:47 Spreker 2

A service provider can offer to my customers.

00:17:50 Spreker 2

These are the services you might want to provision.

00:17:53 Spreker 2

And the customer then selects yes.

00:17:54 Spreker 2

I want version machines and I want email address and whatever and the system then translates this portal then translates this into OK.

00:18:02 Spreker 2

I need to procure deploy now in Microsoft 15 email addresses and I need to create and and and start for instance a Docker instance in my own data center.

00:18:12 Spreker 2

Two provide virtual machines or or specific ISP solution.

00:18:15 Spreker 1

Oh yeah.

00:18:17 Spreker 2

So these are also players in the industry, so it's it's become very I would say.

00:18:22 Spreker 1

Very mixed together, yeah.

00:18:22 Spreker 2

Specialized, now and and and and and.

00:18:26 Spreker 2

You might also want to call these guys platform provider but but but you know This is why you know the web, you know I I can't collect, you know for me.

00:18:35 Spreker 2

How do they monetize?

00:18:35 Spreker 1

We trade within.

00:18:36 Spreker 1

The auto Jack.

00:18:36 Spreker 2

You know?

00:18:37 Spreker 2

How would you describe what are they monetizing?

00:18:39 Spreker 2

This is for me, the way how you differentiate the.

00:18:41 Spreker 2

Guys, because an ISV monetizes software that they they created and packaged OK.

00:18:47 Spreker 2

Yeah, which is very different than you have.

00:18:49 Spreker 2

Somewhere I think in a software developer those actually guys we work with as well in the sense of there are companies.

00:18:55 Spreker 2

Of course, doing individual software development, if you need something which is not available on the shelf somewhere.

00:19:01 Spreker 2

Not from an ISV.

00:19:02 Spreker 2

You go and you pay someone to say I want this piece of.

00:19:05 Spreker 2

Software it needs.

00:19:06 Spreker 2

To look like that, this is what I would call, you know.

00:19:08 Spreker 2

You have it here, a software developer.

00:19:11 Spreker 2

Uhm, you could call them also.

00:19:13 Spreker 2

Like you know these are you know?

00:19:15 Spreker 2

Yeah guys who are.

00:19:19 Spreker 2

Companies who just write, you know, individual software.

00:19:23 Spreker 1

Yeah, for us the software developer roles more like if you need like more manpower to work on your products then you can indeed invest into the software developer.

00:19:32 Spreker 1

So more of an outsourcing.

00:19:33 Spreker 2

Yeah, those will be the Wipro's or or or.

00:19:37 Spreker 2

Yeah, yeah.

00:19:39 Spreker 1

And then we've.

00:19:40 Spreker 1

Got the minister provider which you mentioned.

00:19:41 Spreker 1

Cloud service provider is basically the same but then on the cloud itself instead.

00:19:44 Spreker 2

Yes, and to be honest, we don't differentiate these too much.

00:19:48 Spreker 1

Because also do the same I think or.

00:19:50 Spreker 2

Exactly, and what we actually trying to do is to get the managed they need to manage the service and we need what we're trying to do is to get these guys not managed service in their own.

00:19:58 Spreker 2

Data center, but in our data center and that's about it.

00:20:01 Spreker 1

Exactly and I also have the requirements engineer, uh, I get to work with our products, but that's more on the technical side, which we were thinking of May also have the part of the experts in which you want to partner up with in what's called.

00:20:15 Spreker 1

University or research laboratory or something?

00:20:20 Spreker 1

It's also more despond innovation sites and we want to go into the more sales side of department management.

00:20:28 Spreker 1

So do you think there are any rules missing in this list for example?

00:20:33 Spreker 2

Yeah, so So what?

00:20:33 Spreker 2

You don't call out is the operator channel.

00:20:36 Spreker 2

Uh, which is, at least for us, an important one, and it's specific in the sense that they they are, you know, they they, while they do provide managed services, of course, but they're also reseller and and and.

00:20:49 Spreker 2

And they have also, of course their own network which they're selling, and they provide a lot.

00:20:53 Spreker 2

Of stuff like voice services, which some of the others and you know.

00:20:58 Spreker 2

And maybe it's just for us.

00:20:59 Spreker 2

It's it's but but for us it's an important different channel.

00:21:01 Spreker 2

We we, we kind of and and then you have, you know.

00:21:05 Spreker 2

You know the distributor channel?

00:21:07 Spreker 2

That's a huge one.

00:21:08 Spreker 2

OK and and and while they're not itself, you know they're not selling to end customers, but this kind of role of a multiplier or.

00:21:16 Spreker 2

That's an extremely important one.

00:21:19 Spreker 1

We're thinking to combine that with in reseller because otherwise our list of roles will be too big.

00:21:24 Spreker 1

But now if we can like pick out to Rose Tank and indeed at distributor because they are indeed important, I think for their own like mini ecosystem of their partners and such.

00:21:35 Spreker 2

Right, correct?

00:21:35 Spreker 2

And they're integrating also not only with vendors like Microsoft photos with Isvs, UM.

00:21:43 Spreker 2

They're providing a lot, you know, a lot of of of the basic services to to kind of keep the whole thing going, so yeah.

00:21:49 Spreker 1

Oh, that's great.

00:21:50 Spreker 3

Yeah, and about the the operator role.

00:21:52 Spreker 3

I think you mentioned it before it came.

00:21:54 Spreker 3

Repeat once for once again what it exactly does.

00:21:57 Spreker 2

So, so this is the CPNS of this world of older phones.

00:22:00 Spreker 2

They are mainly selling.

00:22:02 Spreker 2

I don't know, you know you need to ask him what they're selling these days, but they're selling kind of connectivity.

00:22:07 Spreker 2

And based on that they try to add additional services to make again to boost their margin, but also for the vendors.

00:22:14 Spreker 2

This is an extremely interesting channel because the classic reseller channel or whoever you have here, many shares provider selling to a company with two employees is extremely costly because they don't.

00:22:24 Spreker 2

Have a very.

00:22:25 Spreker 2

A scalable structure.

00:22:28 Spreker 2

Uh, you need to be very good and very kind of process driven in order to make money out of a customer that is giving you. I don't know. €30 per month.

00:22:37 Spreker 2

And this is where the operators are really good in.

00:22:39 Spreker 2

OK, UM, and and your whole.

00:22:43 Spreker 2

All your systems, your billing systems, and your provisioning systems and your you name it.

00:22:47 Spreker 2

All of that needs to be extremely streamlined your support mechanisms.

00:22:51 Spreker 2

Because if a guy is calling you once a month, you you know that costs you more than the 30 euros you're going to collect from.

00:22:56 Spreker 2

Them and and this is my.

00:22:58 Spreker 2

This is my.

00:22:58 Spreker 2

This is not only for us but I think for.

00:23:01 Spreker 2

A lot of.

00:23:01 Spreker 2

Vendors, also hardware vendors or whoever you think of.

00:23:05 Spreker 2

It's an extremely important channel.

00:23:07 Spreker 2

Uhm, which?

00:23:08 Spreker 2

Which of course is doing managed service provider or cloud service provider.

00:23:12 Spreker 2

But also you know reselling and and you name it.

00:23:17 Spreker 2

But it's a very distinctive channel which is serving a very I would say, large.

00:23:23 Spreker 2

Proud of or part of the market OK?

00:23:26 Spreker 1

All right, Chris?

00:23:27 Spreker 2

And you can call them telcos, or you know operator whatever you want, OK?

00:23:33 Spreker 1

Could also be a little bit, uh, related to architecture provider or something, or set for a whole difference.

00:23:43 Spreker 2

No, because they actually you know what.

00:23:45 Spreker 2

What they do is they kind of create packages they create package offers for instance where they say OK, you get my you get the line like an Internet access it's company with tracking piece and you get 5 email addresses and you get it.

00:23:57 Spreker 1

Yeah, that's.

00:23:58 Spreker 2

We antivirus solution we spam filter you know decreed the package.

00:24:03 Spreker 2

Solution then is selling and say OK this cost €200 for five users for per month and this is what they're really good in, so they they kind of, you know they're not into a one to one discussion with customers.

00:24:14 Spreker 2

And some of them have it like, like Deutsche Telekom has TI systems as their own system integrator.

00:24:19 Spreker 2

But that's that's again, that's it.

00:24:21 Spreker 2

That's a specific system.

00:24:21 Spreker 1

Just click and play and then go.

00:24:24 Spreker 2

Yeah, but but what they're really good in selling in volume is, like you know you've got 3 seeds.

00:24:29 Spreker 2

Will you get an all in package from us, including the connectivity and what what you need?

00:24:33 Spreker 2

Spam filtering?

00:24:34 Spreker 2

And that other.

00:24:36 Spreker 1

Alright, and one more question about the roles.

00:24:40 Spreker 1

Do you have a distinguish it in what type of partnerships are most important or is that specific to a certain goal?

00:24:47 Spreker 1

You want to achieve.

00:24:50 Spreker 2

It depends.

00:24:51 Spreker 2

It depends because if you ask if you would ask me, hey, for the enterprise business, which was the most important, then I would say system integrators.

00:24:59 Spreker 2

Oh, or ISV's?

00:25:04 Spreker 2

If I'm talking to SMB customers, you know the role of service providers, resellers, distributors.

00:25:12 Spreker 2

This is extremely important, although the ISV role is getting more and more important, uh?

00:25:18 Spreker 2

Also in this space but but yeah, so so so it's there is no one size fits all I would say.

00:25:25 Spreker 1

No, of course not.

00:25:28 Spreker 2

Uh, again you know the requirements, inching difference.

00:25:32 Spreker 2

If I look at this one, you know I would see this as a part of the system integrator to be, or at least for me.

00:25:36 Spreker 2

While it's a role in the system integrator, but this is all like cloud solution architect and whatever you call these guys.

00:25:43 Spreker 2

But you need to find someone who's paying for that, and typically customer is is.

00:25:47 Spreker 2

This is exactly what the big customer would go to a system integrator, say make a kind of an overall, uh, kind of, you know, prepare intender.

00:25:58 Spreker 2

Uh, for me to Cardinal to transform the Dutch Government, to make it whatever the more security, whatever this is, classically something that is done within the system integrator, OK?

00:26:09 Spreker 1

There's a subset of or like an activity of the system created oftentimes.

00:26:13 Spreker 2

Yes yes yes yes.

00:26:16 Spreker 1

Here, let's move on to the goals which you might have.

00:26:20 Spreker 1

So why would you want to invest in those?

00:26:24 Spreker 1

Yeah, yeah, or like the sales partners.

00:26:27 Spreker 1

What type of goals can you have to achieve or to want to invest in those partners?

00:26:33 Spreker 2

So why is Microsoft work with partners?

00:26:35 Spreker 2

That's a very easy one because we can scale through them and uh, and and uh and and we cover each country at the top.

00:26:42 Spreker 2

I don't know in name it Netherlands, maybe 304 hundred customers and I don't know how many commercial customers are.

00:26:47 Spreker 2

Then they lens. I guess a few 100,000, so everything between the top 300 and the complete list of Arnold.

00:26:53 Spreker 2

500

00:26:55 Spreker 2

This is why the partners have to play UM and and and that's it in the end.

00:27:00 Spreker 2

Also sorry someone is ringing or I'll be back in a second.

00:27:02 Spreker 2

Sorry for that.

00:27:02

Oh sure.

00:27:09 Spreker 4

I guess.

00:27:13 Spreker 4

Reset or so.

00:27:14 Spreker 1

The actual office space.

00:27:16 Spreker 4

Mark Beltu lhip only feedback.

00:27:19 Spreker 1

That is, at three comma.

00:27:31 Spreker 4

Differentiate between clouds and clouds.

00:27:34 Spreker 1

Now let's all Heil showmars ideophone nitrous by Ansaldo.

00:27:40

Do you have?

00:27:42 Spreker 4

I think any operator market is that on the short service provider the.

00:27:48 Spreker 1

He doesn't see but deeper serve provider fills man.

00:27:51 Spreker 4

OK.

00:27:57 Spreker 3

All Stars profiling unique position.

00:28:00 Spreker 1

Well managed cloud service provider.

00:28:02 Spreker 1

And then going to cloud service provider owner operator.

00:28:06 Spreker 1

Also provide they are.

00:28:07 Spreker 1

Basically indicating the guest.

00:28:10 Spreker 1

And on this.

00:28:10 Spreker 4

The Garms engineers active part of system integrator.

00:28:13 Spreker 1

That's all I can decide for.

00:28:18 Spreker 1

Bible makes great Auckland like you also detect.

00:28:22 Spreker 1

Thank God.

00:28:30 Spreker 2

Come back, come back, come back, come.

00:28:32

Back, sorry.

00:28:34 Spreker 1

Welcome back.

00:28:36 Spreker 1

So yeah, yeah about the goals that you mentioned.

00:28:40 Spreker 1

Like on average why you want to fetch and partners, but I want to.

00:28:43 Spreker 1

We want to cover like why would you want to?

00:28:46 Spreker 1

Uh, what goal would you like to have or what?

00:28:48 Spreker 1

Why would would you want to?

00:28:50 Spreker 1

To invest in a certain reseller or independence over offender.

00:28:55 Spreker 1

Uh, like more specifically.

00:28:58 Spreker 1

Do you have any distinguished?

00:28:59 Spreker 1

For that or.

00:29:00 Spreker 2

Yes lot.

00:29:02 Spreker 2

Uhm so so so so so.

00:29:04 Spreker 2

The most important thing for.

00:29:05 Spreker 2

US is revenue.

00:29:07 Spreker 2

So that's the number one thing.

00:29:08 Spreker 2

The second thing is kind of the quality of the revenue.

00:29:11 Spreker 2

Like you know what products are the guys selling.

00:29:14 Spreker 2

So we want to invest into resellers that help us sell.

00:29:19 Spreker 2

The I don't know the stuff we want to to to invest invest in.

00:29:23 Spreker 2

So for instance like I said earlier, security, that's a big thing for us.

00:29:26 Spreker 2

OK, we do have reset you know, like like regular email with Office 365, that's like a given for us, but for the time.

00:29:33 Spreker 2

Being we don't.

00:29:35 Spreker 2

You know we're not looking for guys selling our email, OK?

00:29:38 Spreker 2

Uh, but we want to.

00:29:40 Spreker 2

We investing into guys that are doing more security.

00:29:42 Spreker 2

For instance.

00:29:43 Spreker 2

Uh, same is true for a, you know that while we still sell Windows Server or SQL Server and I said you know earlier that we have this holster channel managed service production, we're not investing into this channel.

00:29:56 Spreker 2

We're trying to get these guys from from what you have here from managed service product cloud service provider.

00:30:00 Spreker 2

If they have a question like I want to run my.

00:30:03 Spreker 2

In my data center Windows Server we save figure on your own OK, very black and white OK.

00:30:08 Spreker 2

Uh, the same is true in if someone is selling office on like classic office.

00:30:14 Spreker 2

I don't even.

00:30:14 Spreker 2

Know what their.

00:30:15 Spreker 2

Current versions I think is 2022.

00:30:18 Spreker 2

But this tells you we I don't even know if you want to buy office like a standalone product.

00:30:23 Spreker 2

We're not interested in that anymore.

00:30:24 Spreker 2

We're interested in Microsoft 365 and the security aspects of that OK.

00:30:28 Spreker 2

So so that.

00:30:29 Spreker 2

That's what we're going for, and we do have quite a big set of of of kind of you know, scorecard metrics inside Microsoft.

00:30:36 Spreker 2

And obviously we want to invest into the.

00:30:38 Spreker 2

The the partner channel that is helping us driving these corporate metrics and I'll just give an example.

00:30:43 Spreker 2

So for instance.

00:30:45 Spreker 2

We're interested in kind of winning more in this small business customer space and and this is where we believe, you know, the telcos can help us, and This is why we are all investing actually in them compared to the share of the revenue they have with us.

00:30:58 Spreker 2

Because we believe that they will help us get traction in the in the lower SMP.

00:31:07 Spreker 1

Great yeah yeah.

00:31:09 Spreker 1

Also for our research we also have our own defined set of goals which we'll show you over.

00:31:16 Spreker 1

Second, yeah, so the.

00:31:20 Spreker 1

4 goldbridge or sales related where of course, increasing sales revenue.

00:31:26 Spreker 1

Better enablement of on site system integration.

00:31:30 Spreker 1

Integration of online solutions, and to create more intellectual property through your partner network.

00:31:38 Spreker 1

Yeah, yeah, what do?

00:31:39 Spreker 1

You think about these four goals right now.

00:31:43 Spreker 2

So on site.

00:31:44 Spreker 2

You know this is the as I said.

00:31:45 Spreker 2

You know on premise we're not interested.

00:31:47 Spreker 2

In that anymore.

00:31:48 Spreker 2

If this is happening, that's good.

00:31:50 Spreker 2

We'll take the revenue, but this is nothing where we put any attention to anymore.

00:31:56 Spreker 2

Uhm, creating online solution code some reasonable fees.

00:31:59 Spreker 2

OK yeah, this is what we're that.

00:32:02 Spreker 2

This is what we're doing and this is where we're investing again for Malaysia think.

00:32:12 Spreker 2

Yes, I'm.

00:32:20 Spreker 2

So yes, that's definitely one thing, and creating more intellectual property.

00:32:30 Spreker 2

The thing is.

00:32:33 Spreker 2

So that's an interesting one.

00:32:34 Spreker 2

The last one.

00:32:36 Spreker 2

So so so so number one, yes #2 not for us anymore. #3 yes #4 here in the interesting thing is.

00:32:48 Spreker 2

You know, most of the Isvs they know their **** a lot better than we do.

00:32:53 Spreker 2

OK, so I can't help a guy who is specializing in building a solution for.

00:32:59

I don't know.

00:33:00 Spreker 2

Running wind turbines or whatever you want to call it.

00:33:03 Spreker 2

You know these guys know.

00:33:04 Spreker 2

Their stuff so well.

00:33:06 Spreker 2

I, as a Microsoft guy I can't, you know, I can't tell them.

00:33:11 Spreker 2

Have you thought about this or anything about?

00:33:13 Spreker 2

That you know so, so we are not adding.

00:33:17 Spreker 2

Come we are not helping them.

00:33:19 Spreker 2

You know I can't change them saying oh you think you need to manage your wind turbine in a different way.

00:33:24 Spreker 2

That's not what I can do.

00:33:25 Spreker 2

The only thing what we can do is kind of, you know, help them.

00:33:29 Spreker 2

Kind of you.

00:33:29 Spreker 2

Know maybe run it better or manage their stuff better by moving the cloud service.

00:33:35 Spreker 2

We can help them, maybe add.

00:33:37 Spreker 2

I don't know AI services if this makes sense or integrating.

00:33:42 Spreker 2

I don't know Internet of Things, some millions of sensors integrating that so we can help them.

00:33:48 Spreker 2

With things like that or making it more secure, like saying hey, why don't you use?

00:33:53 Spreker 2

I don't know multifactor authentication things like that.

00:33:57 Spreker 2

But but I would not call this intellectual.

00:33:59 Spreker 2

At least I would not dare to say we're adding intellectual or we help you guys to add intellectual property.

00:34:04 Spreker 2

It's more like we help these guys deliver their intellectual property and their ideas and their visions in a more scalable in a more secure way.

00:34:15 Spreker 2

But these guys have all the insights, OK?

00:34:18 Spreker 1

They're also like thinking like more of a.

00:34:21 Spreker 1

My eyes fees may be too big, but also system is greater.

00:34:24 Spreker 1

They add little pieces on your software, of course to make it fit as their customers.

00:34:29 Spreker 1

I think so, and maybe you feel like, oh by doing these integrations, maybe you get some feedback as well to make that more part of the standardized products or.

00:34:39 Spreker 1

Doesn't it work that way?

00:34:42 Spreker 2

Yes, yes yeah.

00:34:44 Spreker 2

The only thing I mean maybe I'm I'm getting it wrong so so I agree that the goal is increased.

00:34:50 Spreker 2

The value of the product, but this is for me at least. This is the integration piece you have in #3.

00:34:56 Spreker 2

Uh, and.

00:35:03 Spreker 2

Should I say uhm?

00:35:06 Spreker 2

So we want our platform to be used by the guys that have intellectual property, so that's all fine.

00:35:14 Spreker 2

And and and and you're right.

00:35:15 Spreker 2

The goal for us is to increase the value of our product to make.

00:35:17 Spreker 2

It actually interesting.

00:35:19 Spreker 2

You know, for for customers, so that's actually good.

00:35:21 Spreker 2

You know if you read it.

00:35:22 Spreker 2

This way that's a good point.

00:35:23 Spreker 1

Yeah, maybe it's a word.

00:35:24 Spreker 1

It's basically.

00:35:25 Spreker 3

Yes, I think I think the main take away of the the last one is that.

00:35:26

Also just.

00:35:29 Spreker 3

It's not really that.

00:35:31 Spreker 3

You provide intellectual property to user, but they like they, they have some kind of extension.

00:35:37 Spreker 3

On your software.

00:35:39 Spreker 2

Yes, exactly.

00:35:39 Spreker 3

They can help with.

00:35:41 Spreker 2

We we have a platform.

00:35:43 Spreker 2

We provide the platform on which they can.

00:35:47 Spreker 2

Kind of, you know, build and monetized their intellectual property.

00:35:52 Spreker 2

Uhm, because the rest is because it's it's only the first words I'm I'm I'm struggling with a little bit.

00:35:58 Spreker 2

The rest is fine.

00:35:58 Spreker 2

The goal is to increase the value of our platform.

00:36:00 Spreker 1

Yeah yeah, yeah.

00:36:01 Spreker 2

If you call this the product, I'm not adding a value to the Isvs product.

00:36:06 Spreker 2

But they are adding a lot of value to my services, but by making it specific for wind turbine.

00:36:12 Spreker 2

Yeah, manufacturers or whatever and then these guys say well, I'll the the customer is buying the solution and if this solution happens to run on Microsoft platform you know I win OK but but the intellectual property is not coming from me in this case.

00:36:27 Spreker 2

OK, and this one not measuring intellectual property.

00:36:30 Spreker 2

In the end the end customers are measuring that if it's good.

00:36:32 Spreker 2

Enough, the only thing I can do is I can help these guys to make it as easy to run.

00:36:37 Spreker 2

On our platform this.

00:36:38 Spreker 2

Is for sure cool, yes.

00:36:41 Spreker 1

Great, uh, do you?

00:36:43 Spreker 1

Have any goals are missing in this list of four?

00:36:47 Spreker 1

Or do you think they are generally generally applicable?

00:36:51 Spreker 2

Oh, that's good.

00:36:52 Spreker 2

Let me think what else goals do we have?

00:36:57 Spreker 2

You know the operational data dating with a gazillion of goals and the gazillion of.

00:37:01 Spreker 2

Things we're driving or we try to drive.

00:37:04 Spreker 2

But a lot of that in the end boils down to sales revenue.

00:37:09 Spreker 2

The only thing you might want to see as a product as well licenses.

00:37:16 Spreker 2

Integrating almost versions.

00:37:21 Spreker 2

So, So what we want to?

00:37:22 Spreker 2

Drive with partners is actually consumption of online services.

00:37:27 Spreker 2

Because there is a big difference between selling something and actually consuming it, and this is even more true in in an online world because we are paid for.

00:37:36 Spreker 2

Instance on on, on, on on.

00:37:38 Spreker 2

With some of our products we paid on consumed revenue which means the customer can sign up whatever they want as long as they're not consuming the services.

00:37:45 Spreker 2

We're not getting paid for that and this.

00:37:47 Spreker 2

Is where we are working with partners to actually Dr.

00:37:50 Spreker 2

Consumption of sold.

00:37:53 Spreker 2

Services why?

00:37:54 Spreker 2

Because then it then it's becoming sticky and this is for instance and this is both in the enterprise space.

00:37:59 Spreker 2

But also in the in, for instance, the low end space because we had when when I don't know when Telefonica launched.

00:38:06 Spreker 2

One of you know ages ago some of our offerings, they said, yeah, we give one seed of Office 365 free as a kind of giveaway to every commercial customer.

00:38:15 Spreker 2

Because they thought it's a nice marketing activity and.

00:38:19 Spreker 2

And that worked because we made them a great price and then we had.

00:38:22 Spreker 2

I don't know.

00:38:23 Spreker 2

10,100 thousand of theoretical users in Spain. The only thing is none of these guys was ever using it, so the minute they started saying, yeah, you got it up for free for a year.

00:38:33 Spreker 2

Now we're going to charge you for that.

00:38:34 Spreker 2

The guy said, I.

00:38:35 Spreker 2

Don't want it because.

00:38:36 Spreker 2

I never used it so so driving consumption of services is a very important thing.

00:38:43 Spreker 1

A really interesting vacation.

00:38:43 Spreker 2

This is much more important than in an on premise world or on site world wide, because I don't give a **** if the customers using this stuff wants to pay for it.

00:38:52 Spreker 2

And they're not going to buy it again for the next five years anyhow.

00:38:54 Spreker 1

Well, of course.

00:38:55 Spreker 2

But but if I need to renew them or make sure they also pay.

00:38:58 Spreker 2

Me next year.

00:38:59 Spreker 2

Of course I I can say that the customer wants and I can say, hey, you'll need it.

00:39:02 Spreker 2

And this is the greatest thing since the.

00:39:04 Spreker 2

Invention of the wheel.

00:39:06 Spreker 2

But if the guideline is for a year, they're not using it after a year, then I can't come back with the same sales pitch because they can say hey we hit it and we.

00:39:12 Spreker 2

We didn't use it.

00:39:13 Spreker 2

It's not worth the effort.

00:39:14 Spreker 2

Cut it and this is my thriving consumption and is a very important one.

00:39:19 Spreker 2

OK?

00:39:20 Spreker 1

Well, great great take on this unit.

00:39:22

Right?

00:39:22 Spreker 1

Pretty interesting.

00:39:24 Spreker 1

Uh, do you have?

00:39:25 Spreker 1

Anymore for example.

00:39:26 Spreker 1

Or do you think then?

00:39:28 Spreker 1

Those fours with the adults driver consumption.

00:39:33 Spreker 1

Should be it's you think.

00:39:36 Spreker 2

I think, yeah, I think that's it.

00:39:39 Spreker 2

At least the way I would.

00:39:41 Spreker 2

To describe it.

00:39:43 Spreker 2

Which is, you know there is another.

00:39:47 Spreker 2

But but this is also, you know, this might be also a thing.

00:39:50 Spreker 2

You know one thing that would you know, and I'm not sure if if this is in scope of your work or not.

00:39:55 Spreker 2

One thing that we're also trying to get done with the partners actually to.

00:40:00 Spreker 2

To increase the capacity, which means like you know.

00:40:06 Spreker 2

I don't win if partner he hires a grade but have engineer from partner being part by Y wings in this case.

00:40:11 Spreker 2

A part of.

00:40:12 Spreker 2

Me loses and and and if there is always this kind of, you know, lack of resources or skilled resources or whatever you know everyone in the channel is screaming for resources.

00:40:22 Spreker 2

So what we partially also doing is.

00:40:24 Spreker 2

We actually giving money to partners for building new capacity.

00:40:29 Spreker 2

By, for instance, I don't know doing graduate programs and stuff like that.

00:40:35 Spreker 2

Uhm, where we where we kind of really put money on the table and say hey you hire someone from university?

00:40:40 Spreker 2

We know they're not going to be productive for the next two years a lot, because you need to train them a lot, but we'll give you 50% of the salary and I don't know if this is.

00:40:48 Spreker 2

If you see, you know, but but this is more investing into the long term channel or or into the long term.

00:40:54 Spreker 2

Ecosystem and this is something we don't do.

00:40:57 Spreker 2

Extremely proud because we can't afford it, but we do this with with the.

00:41:02 Spreker 2

You know, we know we definitely do this as well to.

00:41:05 Spreker 2

Kind of.

00:41:05 Spreker 2

Of make the ecosystem bigger and we do have some channel.

00:41:10 Spreker 2

Partners that are specialized in that actually you.

00:41:11 Spreker 2

Would add if you want it.

00:41:13 Spreker 2

So the first piece we have a learning channel as well partners that are making money on trainings to customers and to other partners as well.

00:41:22 Spreker 2

It's not a lot of companies per country, but typically you'll find in every country.

00:41:26 Spreker 2

I don't know a handful of companies that make money with that, and this is a very important channel for the long term sustainability of the ecosystem, and also because if you don't get an engineer for a given technology, you know, no matter how much you like it, you can't implement it.

00:41:40 Spreker 1

No, I think that's really, uh.

00:41:44 Spreker 1

They're complementary with this goal, which we had to increase technical capabilities or to outsource.

00:41:51 Spreker 1

Yeah, your your your investments or your technical capabilities.

00:41:55 Spreker 1

So I think that's really.

00:41:56 Spreker 2

Everything outsourcing is not addressing this because outsourcing is just, you know, getting it from somewhere.

00:42:00 Spreker 2

Else but also this is limits.

00:42:03 Spreker 2

Yeah, because outsourcing that's that's a short term fix, but that's not a long term thing.

00:42:07 Spreker 1

No personal.

00:42:07 Spreker 2

And and and and this is where and and and outsourcing has its limits.

00:42:12 Spreker 2

Because you can't outsource the core competency of your company.

00:42:15 Spreker 2

And if your core competency is advising customers on like you know, how do you build an ERP system and how do you implement it?

00:42:22 Spreker 2

You can outsource some.

00:42:23 Spreker 2

Like very I would say, specific tasks, but if you if your competency is.

00:42:29 Spreker 2

Integrating online solutions.

00:42:31 Spreker 2

You can't outsource that, typically.

00:42:33 Spreker 1

No, of course.

00:42:33 Spreker 1

So the the increasing technical capacity is a good thing.

00:42:38 Spreker 1

But the outsourcing is 1 subset of.

00:42:41 Spreker 2

Yeah, OK and and take and and I'm not sure if this is a technological goal, increased capacity, because if you don't have the capacity you you can't deliver anything like increase.

00:42:41 Spreker 1

Yes, I think that.

00:42:51 Spreker 2

This let's you know this is very.

00:42:53 Spreker 2

Linked to each other OK?

00:42:54 Spreker 1

Hi Chris, great to hear.

00:42:56 Spreker 1

We still have about 10 minutes left because we also had an interview with Andre at 10.

00:43:03 Spreker 2

OK, I just booked him earlier.

00:43:03 Spreker 1

So let's go through their method itself because we own some validation on that as well.

00:43:08 Spreker 1

And are you familiar with the process delivered by global diagrams?

00:43:13 Spreker 2

Yes, but yeah, I think so.

00:43:16 Spreker 1

So on the left side here we got the activity parts, uh, which consists out activities you can perform with their respective deliverables, so the concepts.

00:43:29 Spreker 1

So what we first thought of is have you labeled your partner network with roles and which?

00:43:36 Spreker 1

So do you have like a company A has these type of roles is that's true?

00:43:41 Spreker 1

Or is it not something you do?

00:43:47 Spreker 3

Maybe we first have.

00:43:48 Spreker 3

To walk, walk through like the the the whole.

00:43:53 Spreker 2

So saying in in the end you know you know, as as we have an established ecosystem, I could immediately name which are the top posters here.

00:44:00 Spreker 2

The top distributors they are or the top 10 codes somewhere.

00:44:03 Spreker 2

But this is this as I'm saying.

00:44:05 Spreker 2

You know each.

00:44:06 Spreker 2

Part you know and and maybe you.

00:44:07 Spreker 2

Know all these three.

00:44:08 Spreker 2

Roles are the same partner in a given country.

00:44:10 Spreker 2

OK, so so it the question is if you talk about like these roles is is it a very formal thing?

00:44:18 Spreker 1

No one partner capsule for release so yeah.

00:44:19 Spreker 2

Sometimes yes, sometimes no, sometimes yes, sometimes no.

00:44:23 Spreker 1

So then we started with that you want to determine a certain goal.

00:44:29 Spreker 1

So one of the goals which we define.

00:44:32 Spreker 1

Based on that, we, uh, you can select preferred characteristics.

00:44:35 Spreker 1

Uh, we.

00:44:36 Spreker 1

We didn't come to that yet.

00:44:38 Spreker 1

But the the time wanted to do the methods first and then, according to that, you can select partner roles which fits those characteristics.

00:44:47 Spreker 1

So let's say if you have the characteristics of a great network.

00:44:51 Spreker 1

And lots of sales experience that you can.

00:44:57 Spreker 1

And combine certain roles to it.

00:44:59 Spreker 1

Then based on those roles you can select the definitive partners itself and then based on that you can do some sort of investments which is still more of a black box which is like the follow up steps which which are out of the scope.

00:45:14 Spreker 1

And is this a little bit relevant in what you do in real life as well or?

00:45:21 Spreker 1

Yeah, it's it's different.

00:45:25 Spreker 2

I said is it the thing you know?

00:45:28 Spreker 2

How should I say uhm?

00:45:31 Spreker 2

We have a very established channel.

00:45:34 Spreker 2

And and as I said, we're not, you know.

00:45:38 Spreker 2

We're not looking for a lot of extra partners or, or, you know that's wrong, because because we're looking for partners like Isvs more or in certain areas, or we're looking for partners on.

00:45:49 Spreker 2

I don't know security or you name.

00:45:51 Spreker 2

It's so so are we looking for part yes.

00:45:53 Spreker 1

Now we are like determining in which partners in your already established ecosystem you can access to to achieve a certain.

00:46:00 Spreker 1

Goal so if you want to increase more of increasing sales then you can use such methods to.

00:46:05 Spreker 1

Oh well when I follow this this these partners are best suitable to achieving that.

00:46:11 Spreker 1

So and then we kind of test into them.

00:46:14 Spreker 1

Uh, is that something you?

00:46:16 Spreker 1

Or work with search workflow or.

00:46:20 Spreker 1

So it's not not comparing new partners.

00:46:21 Spreker 2

No, because I know which partners.

00:46:23 Spreker 2

If I if I need to drive more revenue I don't make it up in the enterprise space.

00:46:30 Spreker 2

And which is?

00:46:30 Spreker 2

A very complex one because they are, you know, the thing.

00:46:33 Spreker 2

This is all long term, you know, a lot of these things are super long term so I I always kept saying, you know general is like in like an oil tanker.

00:46:39 Spreker 2

If you do something now, it will move in two years from now, or you know that's maybe you know, exaggerating now, but this is not something where you can get like, you know we have an issue now and.

00:46:50 Spreker 2

OK, the next quarter is ending by by June.

00:46:56 Spreker 2

If I put ever if I.

00:46:57 Spreker 2

Push a button.

00:46:57 Spreker 2

Now you know will this.

00:46:58 Spreker 2

Have an.

00:46:59 Spreker 2

Impact part it's very difficult.

00:46:59 Spreker 1

No, of course.

00:47:00 Spreker 2

OK, so This is why and another question is, what would you define with determined goal and and and you know?

00:47:09 Spreker 2

You know there are some things where where where process like that makes sense when it's about like really talking about what is our channel strategy.

00:47:17 Spreker 2

But this has nothing.

00:47:19 Spreker 2

This is a a super long term thing when you think about like do we want to serve cloud services through channels then you might go through some of that.

00:47:26 Spreker 2

But this is not what we do.

00:47:27 Spreker 2

Every day, and once you've made up your channel strategy, it's much more like.

00:47:32 Spreker 2

Executing like from from the part down there.

00:47:37 Spreker 2

But but but are we doing something like that for everything we're doing day-to-day?

00:47:41 Spreker 2

No, because because if you are, if you have a challenge out and SMB business, I know for I don't know for because we want to drive more security to this base.

00:47:50 Spreker 2

I know I need to go to the telcos and integral to the distributors and distributors.

00:47:53 Spreker 2

I have three in each country, trans minors.

00:47:56 Spreker 2

Tell 'cause I have 1/2 in each country so so the number of partners I can go to actually.

00:48:01 Spreker 2

Are often defined more or less by the ecosystem already.

00:48:05 Spreker 2

I don't need to check.

00:48:07 Spreker 2

You know who could be doing it, it's more the other way around.

00:48:09 Spreker 2

I know if I want to drive something in this space, I need to go to tech data Ingram.

00:48:12 Spreker 2

Micro also because these are the three distes I have end.

00:48:16 Spreker 1

So most time the the amount of partners are already small enough to determine, uh, to achieve that certain goal.

00:48:23 Spreker 2

Yes, I know, and and then at the same time you know we do stuff.

00:48:27 Spreker 2

Uhm but but this is an extremely specific and here you know we have a lot of targeting.

00:48:32 Spreker 2

So for instance, when when it's about like you know I'm very technical, you know how do we lend something?

00:48:37 Spreker 2

We actually have a pretty sophisticated.

00:48:39 Spreker 2

AI and machine learning based model that is telling us you know, hey, if I want to lend this specific product into this specific set of customers, these are the right resellers I'll need to talk to.

00:48:51 Spreker 2

And and and and.

00:48:53 Spreker 2

These resellers are typically not working directly with.

00:48:55 Spreker 2

US, but with through.

00:48:56 Spreker 2

Distribution because we only manage a handful of part handful, say 50 partners on average in each country.

00:49:02 Spreker 2

And as I said, with thousands of reserves in each country, we often work them through distribution.

00:49:07 Spreker 2

This is where distribution is very important.

00:49:08 Spreker 2

But we know then.

00:49:10 Spreker 2

Like you know, if I if I want to drive a specific sales play like I want to do security upsell in SMB.

00:49:18 Spreker 2

You know, my system tells me these these are the right to 100 partners. I need to talk to in the Netherlands and then I go to the DC and say, take data.

00:49:26 Spreker 2

Of these, you know these are the 30 partners you need to focus on with this story.

00:49:31 Spreker 2

But but then this whole thing is kind of, you know, coming out already of.

00:49:34 Spreker 2

A system if you.

00:49:35 Spreker 2

Want to call it like that?

00:49:36 Spreker 2

So the system is telling us these are the right and then again you know system only knows is as good as the the stuff you put in.

00:49:43 Spreker 2

And then you know the testing might say, well, actually, this guy might be good as well.

00:49:48 Spreker 2

And and this is where the test is.

00:49:49 Spreker 2

Add a lot of value to us because they know the channel also very well.

00:49:55 Spreker 2

So so is a process like that working.

00:49:59 Spreker 2

It's not on one side.

00:50:00 Spreker 2

Yes, it's formal.

00:50:01 Spreker 2

We haven't implemented the system.

00:50:05 Spreker 2

But but a lot of that is, I would say oral tradition a lot.

00:50:08 Spreker 2

You know your partners.

00:50:10 Spreker 2

You know it's not that formal.

00:50:11

Not sure.

00:50:11 Spreker 2

I would say OK.

00:50:12 Spreker 1

Alright, uh, that's also great here, of course.

00:50:16 Spreker 1

Let's see, do we have anything more now?

00:50:21 Spreker 1

I think due to time we're gonna end.

00:50:23 Spreker 1

It here I.

00:50:23 Spreker 1

Think I want to thank you.

00:50:25 Spreker 1

For your time.

00:50:26 Spreker 1

Of course I would like to say, of course, no.

00:50:26 Spreker 2

OK, I I hope it was useful I.

00:50:28 Spreker 2

Don't know if I was just talking great.

00:50:29 Spreker 1

It is really useful, especially the roles parts and.

00:50:32 Spreker 1

The and the goals to have more defined version of this.

00:50:36 Spreker 1

It's really interesting to us.

00:50:38 Spreker 1

And yeah, would you like?

00:50:40 Spreker 1

To stay up to date with your research or.

00:50:42 Spreker 2

Yeah, of course I would love to.

00:50:44 Spreker 2

I would.

00:50:44

Really love to.

00:50:45 Spreker 1

Yeah, when we finished it we will send it to you and you will also receive a a transcription of the interview so.

00:50:54 Spreker 1

That you filter out.

00:50:55 Spreker 1

Any missing elements or which we have transcribed wrong and.

00:50:59 Spreker 2

No, but I guess.

00:50:59 Spreker 2

It's OK.

00:51:00 Spreker 2

Are you using transcription teams?

00:51:02 Spreker 1

Not yet, but uh, if that's possible, that would be a lot of efforts.

00:51:06 Spreker 2

Actually, I think I I can't see it because I'm not the meeting owner, but but don't you have the feature of transcribing teams?

00:51:14 Spreker 4

Yes, there's a feature.

00:51:15 Spreker 4

It's under the well kind of.

00:51:17 Spreker 4

Do three dots on the right side.

00:51:20 Spreker 2

Yes, exactly, I don't see it because I'm not.

00:51:22 Spreker 2

The guest on this meeting.

00:51:22 Spreker 4

Well, and then there is an option more and then somewhere it should say starts and starts instruction indeed.

00:51:26 Spreker 2

Start transcription yes.

00:51:30 Spreker 1

Can it done?

00:51:31 Spreker 1

But can it be done?

00:51:32 Spreker 1

Backwards, do you think or?

00:51:33 Spreker 2

I have no idea, I'm not.

00:51:34 Spreker 1

I know.

00:51:35 Spreker 2

That good in teams, I'm afraid.

00:51:36 Spreker 1

We'll figure it out.

00:51:39 Spreker 2

Yeah, OK, but next time you ask, Andre Andre is the technical guy you ask Andre he'll he'll explain you OK?

00:51:47

Yeah, crazy.

00:51:48 Spreker 1

Hey, thank you and see you around.

00:51:49

OK.

00:51:50

Yeah, thank you.